

Use case fact-sheet

Actors

List all actors involved in the Use Case and the Geographic Information-related processes they are involved in, then put a “x” in correspondence to the relevant cells.

Who (actor) ²	What (Action) ¹					
	Data acquisition/creation	Data analysis/processing/validation	Data publication	Extraction of information from published data	Data maintenance	xxx
Municipality		x	x			
Decision makers						
Officers/technicians		x		x	x	
Researchers	x	x	x	x		
General Public		x		x		
Citizens	x				x	

Table 1: Overview of the actors involved in the Use Case

Use Case (UC) main info	
Identifier	FE_Floods
Name	Citizen Science – Flooded area detection
Description	<p>Identification and mapping of flooded areas by volunteers participating in the Citizen Science project and automatic estimation of the level and quantity of water present in the area by comparing the data collected with the Digital Terrain Model (DTM).</p> <p>The tool created in this use case elaborates the data about flood-impacted locations collected with quick surveys in order to derive their spatial extension and estimate their water volume. Flooded locations are surveyed as lines: features made of 3 or more vertexes that end up within a custom distance from where they began are considered encircling a flooded area, while the others are considered "linear floods" with a lateral size derived from the field "Larghezza", valued during the survey. A dataset describing building footprints is required in order to avoid considering building parts as part of the flooded areas. Once the surface extension of every surveyed feature is established, features surveyed on the same day and having a spatial overlap are merged, to avoid counting the same area more than</p>

¹ Add new processes or rename the existing ones or split the ones currently merged as you may find more appropriate

² Add new actors or rename the existing ones

	once. The depth of flooded areas and ultimately their volume is determined using a local DTM.
Primary User	Researchers, trained citizen scientists, GIS users
Goal	To provide a first layer of flooded areas in the immediate hours/days after floods from heavy rains. It is also important to keep citizens' attention high on the phenomenon of flooding and encourage participation in the collection of related data
Owner	<i>Piergiorgio Cipriano (Deda Next)</i>
Status	Completed
Policy context	
Challenges & Priorities	Ferrara is located in the Po River basin which means that the river has to be contained by important embankments and the continuous work of the water pumps to prevent the plain from being flooded by water and thus allow rainwater to be directed towards the sea through numerous artificial canals. Climate change affecting the area of Ferrara is resulting in increasingly extreme weather events, including the alteration of normal rainfall levels during different periods of the year. Moreover, Ferrara is increasingly subject to phenomena of intense rainfall and water bombs. For a territory that is almost entirely flat and which tends to flood, extreme rainfall phenomena can cause considerable damage to the city and surrounding municipalities.
Strategy/Plan/Regulation	<p>Hydraulic risk is the subject of multi-level planning with the twofold aim of preventing flood risks in sensitive areas, and avoiding damages related to intense rainfall events in urban areas. The strategic framework incorporates the Flood Risk Management Plan of the Po Valley and Northern Apennines, the Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan as well as the General Urban Plan.</p> <p>Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP), foresees several actions to deal with hydraulic risks. Two of them are particularly relevant for this use case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AD-W1: Preventing hydraulic risks (adaptation action) <p>The adaptation actions concern: monitoring, restoration and strengthening of the territorial protection, adaptation through structural and non-structural interventions, adaptation in the management of artificial reservoirs. The use case can contribute with detailed and near real-time data to identify and characterise areas or stretches prone to flooding.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AD-W2: smart water network <p>The aim of this action is to strengthen the water network resilience in the context of climate change. By mapping risk areas in the city, this use case</p>

	<p>could contribute with the prioritization of interventions on the sewer network and more structural intervention on soil permeability.</p> <p>In the General Urban Plan, an entire Strategic Line of actions is dedicated to support the accomplishment of Ferrara as a resilient and anti-fragile urban landscape.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Objective 1 > Strategic Line 1 > Project Action 1-6
Local Green Deal / City contract(s)	<i>Art 17 PUG rules related to permeability</i>
European Green Deal Policy Area	Adaptation to Climate Change
Precondition	
<p>Actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Groups of volunteers and high schools students (see https://citizenscienceferrara.org/) <p>Data requirement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mapping of the areas most at risk of flooding given by the municipality <p>Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - QFiled app installed on media 	
Postcondition	
DRI (Decision Ready Information)	<p>Mapping of areas subject to flooding after heavy rains.</p> <p>Link to resource: https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/ita/catalog.search#/metadata/e68fc0f1-f55a-4578-9797-4898eac8ae4c</p>
Use of DRI	<p>Quick identification of areas subject to flooding. This dataset doesn't represent an element of absolute scientific value but helps the identification of areas that need assessments regarding permeability and the presence of adequate sewage systems</p>

Use case processing steps	
UC_FE-CS-Floods_BPMN.drawio	
DOI to processing steps BPMN	
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15350770	
Additional remarks	